

Brand and Retailer Initiatives Database

Methodology – Version 1

January 2026

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Document DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18194845](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18194845)

Introduction

To improve the chemical safety and resource efficiency of the food contact materials (FCMs) and articles (FCAs) they use, food brands and retailers from around the world have gone beyond legal requirements by launching hundreds of voluntary initiatives and commitments which they actively communicate to the public. However, this information is spread across many different websites and reports, and it is difficult to systematically find and keep track of.

To make this market-relevant information more accessible, the Food Packaging Forum has created the Brand and Retailer Initiatives Database (BRID) that brings together key information about these voluntary efforts. The database does not rank or review any of the initiatives or commitments included.

Before the publication of this document in 2026, a clearly defined and reproducible, systematic search process for compiling this dataset has not been established, and entries before 2026 have been added on an ad hoc basis as they were identified. Therefore, this document describes a systematic approach to be applied when performing web searches, screening search results, and finally extracting data to be added to the database. Updates and improvements to this methodology can be made in the future.

Definitions

Commitment – A set target to achieve in the future that aims to improve the safety or resource efficiency of food contact materials or articles; often includes a time frame and milestones

Initiative – An action already taken (or started) to improve the safety or resource efficiency of food contact materials or articles

Brand and retailer positive list

A systematically curated, positive list of brands and retailers (see Table 1 for detailed eligibility criteria) is used for the news-search process to identify new commitments or initiatives (referred to collectively as ‘actions’). The list includes food brands, consumer packaged goods (CPG) companies, retailers that sell packaged foods, and major restaurant and fast-food chains. Food contact material and packaging manufacturers are not included. This list is designed to be extensible to allow for increasing the database’s scope.

The list consists of all companies already included in the BRID dataset and will be extended by including additional members from CPG, retail, and restaurant industry associations where the list of member companies is public. In a first step, only major global association lists will be considered, such as Consumer Brand Association, Consumer Goods Forum, Independent Retail Europe, etc. Later, regional and national associations’ members will be added. The brands of large multi-national corporates (e.g. Nestlé, Unilever, PepsiCo, The Coca-Cola Company, etc.) will be included additionally.

Table 1: Eligibility criteria for companies to be included or excluded in the positive list.

Inclusion	Exclusion
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Any company that produces packaged foods• Any company that sells packaged foods• Restaurant and fast-food chains• Food delivery services• Any retailer that sells packaged foods	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Food contact material and packaging manufacturers• Companies that exclusively sell non-food consumer packaged goods (e.g., cosmetics)• Small local standalone restaurants• Exclusively non-food delivery services (e.g., postal services)• Exclusively non-food retailers (e.g., clothing, cosmetics, department stores, etc.)

Keyword list

A list of relevant keywords will be used to complement the news-search alongside the brand and retailer positive list. This keyword list is based on word frequency from all existing data entries in the BRID, up until December 2025, and comprises relevant words that occurred at least 50 times and variations of specific words (e.g., recycle,

recycling, recycled). Additional words can be added as necessary, based on the analysis of future search results.

Tool and information source

The news-monitoring process is conducted using [Inoreader](#), a web-based content and RSS feed aggregator that compiles updates from a wide range of online sources. All information collected originates from publicly accessible websites indexed through Google News.

Search strategy

A custom set of feeds is configured to capture news articles that include any brand or retailer listed on the internal positive list, in combination with any keyword from the keyword list (Figure 1). Title and content of searched news articles are considered for this.

The search parameters are restricted to English-language articles. Additional languages could be added in the future depending on monitoring capacity.

Figure 1: Search strategy set up showing "or" and "and" operators applied.

Screening

Articles are screened for inclusion in the BRID database using defined criteria. An article is considered eligible if it (1) describes a commitment or initiative – as defined earlier – by a company on the positive list, or (2) reports on the cancellation of such a commitment or initiative. Examples for commitments or initiatives include switching from one material to a safer and/or more sustainable option (e.g., switching from single-use plastic bottles to reusable glass bottles), pledging to increase the percentage of reusable packaging, increasing post-consumer recycled content in packaging, or phasing out chemicals of concern in food contact materials (see Table 2 for further details).

Table 2: Eligibility criteria for commitments and initiatives.

Inclusion	Exclusion
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Reduction in plastic FCMs• Increasing post-consumer recycled content in FCMs• Increasing percentage of reusable FCAs• Optimized product design for reuse (e.g., sturdier materials, non-single-use closures)• Optimized product design for recycling (e.g., multi-material to mono-material, recyclable materials)• Phasing out or avoiding chemicals of concern in FCMs• Improved resource efficiency (e.g., reduction in article weight, removal of non-essential components)• Increase in compostable FCMs• Increase in bio-based FCMs• Switching from non-inert FCMs (e.g., plastics, paper) to more inert materials (e.g., glass, stainless steel, glazed ceramics)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Any commitment or initiative that does not relate to food contact materials or articles• Changes in design for marketing and branding purposes

Data extraction

For each news article that meets the inclusion criteria, the following data points are extracted:

- a description of the item (e.g., specifics of the action like which chemicals are being phased out, exact reusability targets, etc.)
- assigned keywords (e.g., “reuse” for commitments on increasing reusable packaging)
- the name and type of the brand or retailer
- the name of the brand owner if applicable (e.g., Lay’s is owned by PepsiCo)
- year or timeline of the initiative or commitment
- the country or region where the initiative or commitment applies
- whether the action refers to chemicals

- whether the action is a commitment or an initiative
- whether the item describes the cancelation of a previous commitment
- the date the action was reported
- the public link to the reported action

Frequency of screening and updates

The search is conducted on a monthly basis. Updates to the database derived from this process are compiled and entered each quarter.

Limitations

Limiting the language of considered news articles to English does not paint a fully global picture and will put a focus on larger international companies that are usually covered in English media, or primarily English-speaking regions. While Google News is one of the largest collections of news articles, some sources may be left out.

In addition, this search method only covers commitments and initiatives that are covered by news outlets. In the future, the search could be extended beyond Google News to search for any relevant websites or even companies' annual and investor reports.

There will be a bias towards larger organisations that prioritize such issues because they are PR relevant. Smaller, less well-known brands likely will not actively communicate packaging-related internal policies but may still have them.

Currently, we do not have any mechanism to verify the credibility of sources. This can be remediated in the future by validating third-party reporting with the brand's official communications.